

Demand for Long-Acting Family Planning Methods and Associated Factors Among Family Planning Service Users in Public Health Centers, Debre Birhan, Ethiopia

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Abstract

Background: Long-acting family planning methods are in high demand in order to improve reproductive health and lower the number of unwanted pregnancies. Even though long-acting family planning methods are quite effective, they are still not widely used, especially in low- and middle-income nations. Evidence indicates that the majority of women were dependent on short-acting contraceptive methods, despite the fact that long-acting methods are safer, more effective, and offer protection against unplanned pregnancy.

Objectives: The objectives of this study are to assess the demand of long-acting family planning methods and identify associated factors among family planning service users in Debre Birhane public health centers of Amhara region, Ethiopia.2025

Methods: An institutional-based cross-sectional quantitative approach was conducted from February 1st to March 30th 2025. A sample size is 394 and systematic random sampling was employed for selecting study units. A pretested structured questionnaire was used to collected data from the study participants. For data entry KOBO tool box was used and transferred to SPSS version 27.0.1 for data process and analysis. Descriptive statistics used to describe study variables. Bivariate and multivariable regression analysis done with 95% confidence intervals and a p-value <0.05 considered to declare statistically significant associations lastly result presented using a text and table.

Result The study included 390 respondents with 99% respondent rate. The demand for Long-acting family planning method was 100 (25.6%). Marital status, Multigravida, Information from mass media, good attitude on Long-acting family planning method, Age 35-49, education No formal education, age at marriage 25-35 and being student at high school and above and reproductive age group. Affect the demand for Long-acting family planning method in this study.

Conclusion: the demand for Long-acting family planning method according to this study was low and the unmet need for Long-acting family planning method also high. Marital status, Multigravida, Information from mass media, good attitude on Long-acting family planning method, Age 35-49, education No formal education, age at marriage 25-35 and being student at high school and above and reproductive age group. Affect the demand for Long-acting family planning method in this study.

Recommendation: - Based on this study the demand for long acting family planning method is low and unmet need for Long-acting family planning method was found high so it is better to utilize the opportunity to provide the service to meet.

Keywords: Demand, Long-Acting Family Planning, Reproductive age women, meet need, unmet need.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

A key element of reproductive health, family planning (FP) helps people and couples to plan for and achieve the number of children and spacing of births they wish.(1). It encompasses a range of practices and methods that allow people to make informed choices about their reproductive lives (2). By giving people more control over their reproductive health, FP lowers the number of unwanted births, improves maternal and child health, and gives women the confidence to seek higher education and employment. (3, 4).People utilize FP for numerous reasons, including the desire to limit family size, space births, and improve overall family well-being (5). Effective family planning can lead to healthier pregnancies and births, as well as enhanced economic conditions for families by allowing parents to allocate resources more effectively (6). Additionally, FP plays a crucial role in reducing maternal mortality rates, as it enables women to avoid high-risk pregnancies and childbirths (7). The ability to plan and space pregnancies is particularly important in regions with high fertility rates, where access to FP services can significantly impact public health and socio-economic development(8).

The demand for effective FP methods is a critical aspect of reproductive health, particularly in low and middle-income countries (LMICs), where unintended pregnancies can have significant socio-economic consequences (9). Among the various contraceptive options available, long-acting contraceptive methods (LACMs) such as intrauterine devices (IUDs) and hormonal implants stand out due to their high efficacy and convenience. Unlike short-acting methods, LACMs require minimal user intervention once administered, making them an appealing choice for many women seeking to prevent unintended pregnancies(3).

The demand for the use of LAFPMs is related to various factors. Therefore, it's critical to evaluate the demand for LAFPMs among FP service users in order to pinpoint different socio demographic, cultural, and health system elements. In the end, better family planning alternatives for women can result from comprehending and addressing the issues that affect the demand for LAFPMs. This will assist to lower the rates of unwanted births and improve general reproductive health.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Despite their advantages, the uptake of Long-Acting family planning Methods remains low in worldwide. Every year approximately 350,000 women die while pregnant or giving birth, and of which 99% of women die in developing countries (10). An estimated 8 million more women suffer serious illnesses and lifelong disability as a result of complication during childbirth. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), less than 10% of women in many LMICs use LAFPMs, compared to significantly higher rates in high-income countries (11). Sub Saharan Africa countries faces serious population and reproductive health challenges, which is indicated by higher maternal mortality, higher total fertility and population growth rate, and higher unmet need for FP(12). For instance, the unmet need of FP in LMICs range from 20% up to 58% (9). In Ethiopia, from 871 per 100,000 live births in 2000 to 412 per 100,000 live births in 2016, Ethiopia's maternal mortality ratio has decreased. Ethiopia's maternal mortality ratio, according to the UN Interagency Maternal Mortality Ratio projection for 2020, is 267 per 100,000 live births, indicating considerable progress in reducing maternal mortality, however it is still far behind the SDG target of 70(13).The total fertility rate of Ethiopia is 5.4 children per women, population growth rate is estimated at 2.7% per year, contraceptive prevalence rate is only 15% and an unmet need for FP is 34%(14). Addressing the unmet need of FP in Ethiopia is expected to avert 12,800 maternal deaths and more than 1.1 million child deaths (15). The demand for LAFPMs is a critical area of study, particularly in LMICs, like Ethiopia, where the rates of unintended pregnancies remain alarmingly high (16). Despite providing long-term and efficient family planning options, LAFPMs are frequently underutilized because of a number of obstacles. Improving reproductive health outcomes and lowering mother and newborn morbidity and death linked to unwanted pregnancies require an understanding of the factors that affect demand for these techniques. (17, 18).

Enhancing access to LAFPMs can significantly decrease the incidence of unsafe abortions and related complications, thereby positively impacting public health (19).Most of the studies have been conducted on met need of long-acting family planning methods in the general population; however, there was limited number of research on unmet need and demand for long-acting family planning methods among family planning users in Debre Birhane. Similarly, there was no published study conducted to assess the level of demand for long-acting family planning methods and associated factors in Debre Birhane.

1.3 significance of the study

The evidence-based identification of gaps and related factors for the demand for long-acting family planning and factors among Debre-Birhane family planning users is the main significance of this study. Therefore, based on the degree of influence that the study's findings may have, this study aims to explain the demand for long-acting family planning methods and the factors that influence the target clients' use of such family planning. It also suggests goal-oriented, responsive, and scientific interventions that may increase ownership and commitment among all the relevant bodies to strengthen service utilization.

The findings from this study will help policy makers and planners and other concerned organizations working in the area of family planning and maternal health to meet the demand of long-acting contraceptive methods.

2 Literature review

2.1 Utilization of Long-Acting Family planning

By 2020, the reproductive health program projected maternal mortality to decline to 199 per 100,000 live births and neonatal mortality to 10 per 1,000, underscoring the role of family planning in reducing maternal deaths (20). In Indonesia, only about 10% used long-acting family planning methods (LAFPMs) such as implants and IUDs (21), while a Sudanese study reported IUD use at 10.2% and Implanon at 14% (22). In Ethiopia, injectables remain the most common method among married women (27%), followed by implants (9%), and pills and IUDs (2% each). Modern contraceptive use increased from 14% in 2005 to 41% in 2019, with implant use rising from <1% to 9% during the same period. Utilization is higher among wealthier women (27% in the lowest vs. 51% in the highest quintile), those with fewer children (53% with 1–2 vs. 31% with ≥ 5), urban residents (48% vs. 38% rural), and those with secondary education (56% vs. 32% with no education). Regional variation is substantial, with highest use in Amhara (50%) and Addis Ababa (48%) and lowest in Somalia (3%) and Afar (13%) (20).

In the Sidama region, 37.8% of women used reversible LAFPMs (95% CI: 32.9–42.7), including 9.6% with IUDs and 28% with implants (23). In Addis Ababa, demand for LAFPMs was high (76.7%), yet unmet need remained substantial (40.7%). Factors influencing demand included marital status, gravidity, awareness, attitudes, and perceived quality of services (24). Despite national policy priorities,

central Ethiopia continues to have the lowest uptake of LAFPMs, highlighting the need to explore barriers and enablers of utilization (25).

2.2 Demand for Long-Acting Contraceptive Methods

A survey in Iran reported a 71.4% demand for LAFPMs, with 27.7% actual use (26). In South Africa, women often lack autonomy in contraceptive choice (27), while studies in Kenya and Nigeria found utilization rates of 18% and 38.7%, respectively (28,30). In Uganda, 4% of mothers had never heard of family planning services (29).

Sub-Saharan Africa continues to face high fertility, maternal mortality, and unmet family planning needs, particularly for long-acting methods, with rural women disproportionately affected (31). In Nepal, uptake of LACMs was 11% (32). In Ethiopia, findings vary: Northwest Ethiopia showed demand at 17% (10,33), Oromia at 28.4% (34), and Amhara ranging widely from 51.1% in West Gojam (7) to as low as 12.9% in Janamora District (38). In Debre Tabor, 9.2% used long-acting methods (8.2% Implanon, 1% IUCD), with 7.8% unmet need, mostly for spacing (39). In Southeast Ethiopia, 8.7% were current users (mainly Norplant), with highest use among women aged 25–29 but declining with age; prevalence in Mekelle was 14% (40). In Asosa town, demand was 62.9%, influenced by age, marital status, education, and socioeconomic status (41).

Across studies, cultural beliefs, misconceptions, availability of services, and provider competence significantly influence contraceptive use. Identifying these barriers is essential to increasing demand and uptake of LAFPMs (42).

2.3 Factors affecting Long Affecting Family Planning

2.3.1 Socio demographic factors

The demand for LAFPMs is associated with various sociodemographic and behavioral factors. In Gondar City, women with education beyond secondary school were nearly three times more likely to use LAFPMs (AOR = 2.91) (36). Young women with a history of induced abortion were 3.75 times more likely to use LAFPMs (32), and those under 20 were 1.78 times more likely than older women. Husbands' occupation also mattered: women whose partners were day laborers were 4.4 times more likely to use LAFPMs (43).

Past use strongly predicts current use. In Goba town, women with prior LAFP experience were over 17 times more likely to use it again (AOR = 17.43, 95% CI: 9.19–33.03). Frequent discussions about LAFP also increased uptake more than fourfold (AOR = 4.6, 95% CI: 1.72–12.17), while intention to use predicted future demand (40). In Mekelle, women with moderate knowledge were six times more likely to use LAFP (AOR = 5.9), and those with high knowledge nearly eight times more likely (AOR = 7.8). Multiparous women were also more likely to use LAFP than primiparous ones (AOR = 2.7, 95% CI: 1.4–5.1) (14).

In Debre Tabor, demand for LAFP was 17%, though only 9.2% were actual users, and 7.8% had unmet need (39). Factors positively associated with demand included having five or more children (AOR = 1.67), joint decision-making with husbands (AOR = 2.73), being a student (AOR = 2.64), not desiring future children (AOR = 2.17), and frequent spousal discussions. Occupational status also influenced demand, with day laborers showing higher use (AOR = 3.87) (10).

2.3.2 Individual factors

Individual-level barriers include poor provider-client interactions, limited counseling, and concerns over safety or side effects. A study in Debre Birhan highlighted that inadequate care from health workers reduced demand for LAFPMs, underscoring the role of provider communication in shaping contraceptive uptake (44).

2.4 Conceptual framework of the Demand for long-acting family planning and factors among family planning

Conceptual frame work has been developed or adapted from this paper after a rigorous review of the relevant literatures. As shown in the figure socio-demographic factors, individual behavioral factors, predisposing factors and reproductive history of the mother have a link with demand for long-acting family planning methods.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework or demand for long-acting family planning methods users in public health centers, Debre Birhane. Ethiopia, 202 ([28](#), [30](#), [36](#)).

3 Objectives

3.1 General objectives

To determine the demand for long-acting family planning methods and identify associated factors among family planning service users in Debre Birhan public health centres, Amhara region, Ethiopia 2025.

3.2 Specific objectives

To determine the demand for long-acting family planning methods among family planning service users in Debre Birhan public health centers.

To identify associated factors for the demand of long-acting family planning methods among family

planning service users in Debre Birhan public health centers.

4 Materials and Methods

4.1 Study area and period

The study was conducted in Debre Birhane public health centers of Amhara region of Ethiopia. Debre Birhane town is located in the northeast part of the Amhara region, and it is 130 km far from Addis Ababa, the capital city of Ethiopia and 695 km away East of Bahir Dar. According to 2022 administrative report, a total population of Debre Birhane is 209, 011. and has five sub city 8 health center 2 public hospital and 1 private hospital and 13 clinics are in Debre Birhane city. The study was conducted from February 1 up to March 30, 2025. in Debre Birhane public health centers.

4.2 Study design an institutional based cross-sectional study design was used.

4.3 Populations

4.3.1 Source population

All family planning service users reproductive age women of Debre Birhane are the source population from which the study population was drawn.

4.3.2. Study population

Family planning service users who was selected with a systematic random sampling method from all family planning service users based on a calculated flow rate of service user's interval was the study population in Debre Birhane governmental health centers.

4.3.3 Study unit

Family planning service users selected by simple random sampling techniques who was data collected during study period.

4.4 Eligibility criteria

4.4.1. Inclusion criteria

All women, who are active FP service users, and available in Debre Birhane public health centers during the study period was included.

4.4.2. Exclusion criteria

Those who are seriously ill and enable to communicate in the study was excluded from the study.

4.5. Sample size determination

A single population proportion formula is used to determine the total required sample size. The sample is calculated using the assumption of a significance level CI of 95%, a 5% margin of error, and demand for long-acting family planning methods was used from a previous study done in Assosa Town shows that, 62.9% of the respondent had demand for LAFPM. a 62.9% population proportion (42).

A 10% from the total sample is considered or added for a non-response rate. At 95% confidence level (CI), $p=0.629$, and $d= 0.05$., $N=[(Z_{\alpha/2})^2 * P (1-P)]/d^2$, $N=[(1.96)^2 * 0.629(1-0.629)]/(0.05)^2 = 358.6$

With 10% for non-response rate, then the total sample will be $358.6 + (358.6 \times 10\%) = 394$.

Table 1 Sample size calculation for the second objective from similar study Utilization of long-acting contraceptive methods and associated factors among married women in Farta Woreda, Northwest Ethiopia(45).

Factors	outcome in unex	outcome in ex	CI	power %	sample	A %	Total
Educational level	90%	69.8%	95%	80	142	14	156
Previous use of LAFPM	92.8%	76.1%	95%	80	14	1	15
Attitude	93.4%	77.6%	95%	80	178	17	195
Having numbers of children	97.2%	30.9%	95%	80	38	3	41

By considering both the first and second objectives the maximum sample size is 358 from the First objective, to get the final sample size with adding the 10% non-respondent rate $358 + (358 \times 10\%) = 394$.the

sample size is 394. Since the output for objective one.

Sampling technique and procedure

A simple random sampling techniques was used to select the study participants in Debre Berhan public health centers. 5 health centers are randomly selected from 8 health centers in Debre Brhane town. Then, the study participants was selected randomly using a lottery method. The number of study participants was allocated proportionally for each public health centers. Then the respondent subject was selected from selected health centers by using systematic random sampling based on the family planning service client’s flow three months average numbers. The overall sampling procedures and sample allocation techniques looks like in the following table.

Table2 Sample size proportional allocation for demand for long-acting family planning e methods users in public health centers, Debre Birhane. Ethiopia, 2025.

HEALTH CENTERS IN DEBREBRIHANE TWON RANDEMLLY SELECTES	AVARAGE NUMBERS OF CLIANTS FOR THREE MONTHS	NUMBER OF SAMPLE PROPORTIONAL TO ALL
04 HEALTH CENTER	1550	163
TEBASSE HC	650	68
AYER TENA HC	715	75
CHACHA HC	450	47
MINILIC HC	385	41
Total	3750	394

Debre Birhane city have 8 Health Center Then 5 Health Centre’s selected randomly proportional allocation of Sample drawing selected from health centers.

Debre Birhane has 8 health centers are giving family planning services all type, 5 of them selected using simple random sampling and the sample size is allocated proportional to the monthly number of family planning user of each Health Center

Figure 2: proportional allocation of Sample drawing techniques for demand for long-acting family planning methods users in public health centers, Debre Birhane, Ethiopia, 2025.

4.6. Study variables

4.6.1. Dependent variable

Demand of long-acting family planning methods

4.6.2. Independent variable

- Socio demographic characteristics of clients
- Knowledge of respondent about long acting family planning method
- Attitude of respondent regarding family planning methods
- Reproductive history of respondent
- Source of information

These independent variables were selected because different previous studies show association with the dependent variable i.e. demand for long-acting family planning.

4.7. Operational definition

LAFPMs: The reversible LAFPMs such as IUD and Implant are considered as LAFPMs.

Demand for LAFPMs: It is determined by adding both the proportion of women who are using long acting family planning methods (met need) and proportion of women who are using any other short acting family planning methods but want to use LAFPMs (unmet need) (10).

Unmet need for long-acting family planning methods: - Women who desired to use Implant or IUCD for spacing or limit pregnancy but did not use the methods due to any reason.

Met need for long-acting family planning methods: - Women who use Implant or IUCD.

Attitude: The attitude of women towards LAFPM will be assessed using ten negatively stated attitude related questions, and maximum score was given when participants strongly disagree for the questions and lower points when they strongly agree. The attitude will be labeled as positive attitude for those participants who will be scored above the mean, and negative attitude for those participants who will be

scored below or equal to the mean score ([14](#), [33](#)).

Knowledge of long-acting contraceptive methods: This study suggests that a woman is considered to be good knowledge about long-acting family planning techniques if she cites Mean and above. And poor knowledge is of them answer less than the mean ([14](#)).

4.8. Data collection method

A Structured interview questionnaire was developed from various studies. A clean, and unambiguous questionnaire was prepared in the English language. The questionnaire was translated into the Amharic version. The pretest was conducted 10% of total sample size =40 at Debre Birhane referral hospital. For each health facility, two data collectors and was recruited and trained. The questionnaire was pre-tested to ensure uniformity. The supervisors and data collectors received adequate training on the data gathering procedure. Supervisors evaluated and verified the completeness of the questionnaires daily throughout the data collecting period, and every other day by the lead investigator and all required input was give. After all the data is collected, the data was entered, labeled, and cleaned using SPSS software.

4.9. Data quality management

To ensure data quality, all data collectors and supervisors was receive training and proper orientation before the actual starting of data collection. To maintain consistency, the English version of the questionnaire was translated into the Amharic language and then back into English. Two weeks before the data collection, the questionnaire was pre-tested on 10% of the study population in the Debre Birhane hospital FP unit with a similar population, and a few modifications was made. Furthermore, the accuracy, clarity, and completeness of data was reviewed daily by the principal investigators.

4.10. Data processing and analysis

The data was undergo verification for completeness, and the Kobo tool box used to data entry and subsequently exported to the SPSS Version 27 software for analysis. Descriptive statistics was calculated, including mean and standard deviation for continuous variables, as well as frequencies and percentages for categorical variables. Check the reliability of the questionnaire and the validity of the variable was tested using Cronbach alpha (0.63 for likert scale variable). Hosmer-lemeshow test is done for goodness of fit and calibration for logistic regression models. Each variable was be assessed for normality and the

satisfaction of assumptions utilizing histograms, boxplots, and scatter plots before analysis. The binary logistic regression was used and its assumptions such as multicollinearity and model fitness will be assessed using variance inflation factors (VIF). The results was described using tables, charts, graphs. A variable in bivariate logistic regression with a p-value less than or equal to 0.25 was selected as a candidate for further multivariable analysis. Finally, the association between dependent variables and factors was presented using adjusted odd ratio, and its 95% confidence interval and a p-value of less than 0.05 in multivariable analysis will be consider statistically significant.

4.11. Ethical considerations

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) and supporting latter from Debre Birhane University, Asrat Woldeyes Health Science Campus. A Verbal informed consent was obtained from the study participants. The data privacy and confidentiality was in secured form and used only to meet the objective of this research study. And the study was follow the of Debre Birhane university Asrat Woldeyes health compass institutional review board ethical guidelines.

4.12. Result dissemination plan

The findings disseminated to Debre Birhane University Asrat Woldeyes Health Science Campus department of public health in partial fulfillment for Masters of public health. The findings and recommendations will be distributed to all public health centers, the Debre Birhane town health department and other organizations working on related areas to be used as a baseline for interventions.

5 Result and Discussion

5.1. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENT

A total of 390 family planning users have participated in this study with response rate of 99%. The mean age of the women was 28.79 and SD ± 5.85 years. Similarly the majority of 173 (44.4%) of participants were also married. Regarding school enrolment; the majority 168 (43.1%) of the respondents had elementary education, followed by 128 (32.8) with no formal education and the other 69 (17.7%) had some diploma or higher education level. Regarding the occupation status of respondents about 108 (27.7%), were engaged in private business and the rest were government and non-government employees.

Table 3 Socio-demographic characteristics of respondent among women who attend family planning service at Public health facilities in Debre birhane city (2025) (n=390).

	Category	Frequency	Percent%
Age	15-24	145	37.2
	25-34	152	39
	35-49	93	23.8
Marital status	Single	81	20.7
	Married	173	44.4
	Divorced	24	6.6
	Widowed	112	28.7
Educational status	No formal education	128	32.8
	Primary/Elementary	168	43.1
	Secondary	25	6.4
	Diploma and above	69	17.7
Occupation	Daily laborer	33	8.5
	Government employee	86	22
	Non-government em	28	7.2
	Housewife	74	19
	Private business	108	27.7
	Student high school >S	19	4.9
	Unemployed	42	10.8
Religion	Catholic	16	4.1
	Muslim	63	16.2
	Orthodox	268	68.7
	Protestant	43	11
Husband/partner educational status	No formal education	13	3.3
	Primary/Elementary	183	46.9
	Secondary	59	15.1

5.2 DEMANDED AND UTILIZATION OF LAFPM

The current utilization proportion of the demand for LAFPM was 100 (25.6%). Among demanded LAFPM, 35 (35%) met need and 65 (65%) unmet need LAFPM in the town Demand for LAFPM in the study was 100 (25.6%). This was the sum of current use of LAFPM (met need) and the method desired but not used due to any reason (unmet need). Current long acting family planning users (met need) were 35 (35.0%) and unmet need were 65 (65%).

Table 4 Demand and utilization of LAFPM among women who attend family planning service at public Health facilities in Addis Ababa, 2017(n=390).

Variables	Options	Frequency	Percent
Utilization of LAFPM(Either Implant or IUCD) before	Utilize	192	56.4
	Not utilize	179	43.6
Demanded LACM(Either IUCD or Implant) current	Demanded	100	25.6
	Not Demanded	290	74.4
Status of Demand Meet	Meet Need	35	35.0
	Unmet Need	65	65.0
	Not Demanded	290	74.4
Ever used implant	Yes	198	50.8
	No	192	49.2
Ever used IUCD	Yes	22	22.6
	No	368	77.4
Ever used any family planning	Yes	376	96.4
	No	14	3.6
Those get information about family planning method	Yes	270	69.2
	No	120	30.8
Current method used is by choice	Yes	274	70.25
	No	116	29.75
Waiting time	Reasonable waiting time	290	74.4
	Too long waiting time	100	25.6

Demand for LAFPM

Figure 3 bar chart show demand to long acting family planning and has no demand for demand for long-acting family planning methods users in public health centers, Debre Birhane. Ethiopia, 2025.

5.3 REPRODUCTIVE HISTORY OF THE MOTHER

Regarding the reproductive history of mother; the minimum age at first marriage was 17 years and maximum was 35 years. Similarly the minimum age at first birth of mothers was 18 years and the maximum was 36 years. Among mothers interviewed, (279, 71.5%) ever gave birth.

Table 5 :Reproductive histories of respondent among women who attend family planning service at public health facilities in Debre birhane, 2025(n=390)

	Category	Frequency	Percent%
Ever gave birth	Yes	279	71.5
	No	111	28.5
Number of births	Nulliparous	138	35.4
	Primi(1 birth)	174	44.6
	Multiparty>2	78	20
Number of alive children	0-2	64	16
	3 or 4	38	9.7
	>4	170	43.6

5.4 INFORMATION & SOURCE ON FAMILY PLANNING METHODS

Regarding the information on contraceptive method majority (90.3%) of the respondent heard about LAFPM and (49%, 30.7%) mothers have heard about implant and IUCD respectively. Majority (41.4%) of the respondent heard information from health professionals.

Table 6 Health information exposure statues among women who attend family planning service at public health facilities in debre birhne (n=390)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent%
Ever heard about long-acting contraceptive method	Yes	352	90.3
	No	38	9.7
Source of information	Health professional	146	41.4
	Husband	78	22.2
	Mass media	73	20.7
If yes what type of LAFPM have you heard	Relatives	55	14.1
	Implant	173	49
	IUCD	108	30.7
	Implant and IUCD	71	20.2

5.5 Knowledge of respondents on family planning

Regarding the knowledge of women on IUCD method knows that it prevents pregnancy, it does not prevent STI and it does not interfere sexual intercourse (56.9%, 50.5%, 57.7%) respectively. Similarly, knowledge of women on implant knows that it prevents pregnancy, it does not interfere sexual intercourse and pregnancy reverse quickly when implant removed (70%, 58.2% and 30.3%) respectively. Composite score of Knowledge on LAFPM 312 (80%) has good knowledge, and 78 (20%) has Poor knowledge.

Table 7 Knowledge of respondents on family planning methods among women who attend family planning service at public health facilities in Debre birhane (n=390)

Knowledge Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent%
IUCD prevent pregnancy	True	222	56.9
	False	67	17.2
	Not sure	101	25.9
IUCD prevent STI	True	110	28.3
	False	197	50.5
	Not sure	83	21.3
IUCD interferes with sexual intercourse or desire	True	113	29
	False	225	57.7
	Not sure	51	13.1
Implant prevent pregnancy	True	273	70
	False	89	22.8
	Not sure	29	7.4
Implant interferes with sexual intercourse or desire	True	142	36.4
	False	227	58.2
	Not sure	21	5.38
Implant reverse pregnancy quickly when removed	True	118	30.3
	False	115	29.5
	Not sure	157	40.3
Composite score of Knowledge on LAFPM	Good knowledge	312	80
	Poor knowledge	78	20

5.6 ATTITUDE OF RESPONDENT FOR LAFPM

In general, about (74.1%, 25.9%) of respondents have positive and negative attitude towards the methods respectively.

Table 8 Attitude of respondents on LAFPM among women who attend family planning service at public health facilities in Debre birhane health centers(n=390)

Attitude Variable	Options	Frequency	Percent%
Implant cause irregular menses and painful	Agree	118	30.3
	Not sure	147	37.7
	Disagree	125	32.1
IUCD insertion cause loss of privacy	Agree	64	16.4
	Not sure	184	47.2
	Disagree	142	36.4
IUCD restrict normal activity	Agree	63	16.2
	Not sure	135	34.6
	Disagree	192	49.2
Long-acting method safer and more effective than short acting	Agree	190	58.7
	Not sure	141	36.2
	Disagree	59	15.1
Recommend long-acting method to others	Agree	229	58.7
	Not sure	112	28.7
	Disagree	49	12.6
Composite Attitude score of respondents on LAFPM	Positive attitude	289	74.1
	Negative attitude	101	25.9

5.7 MULTIVARIABLE ANALYSIS

After bivariate analysis variables those shows association at 0.25 level of significance was transferred in to multivariable analysis to control confounding variables and test the association of each variable with the dependent variable. The demand for LAFPM was 100 (25.6%). Among demanded LAFPM, 35 (35%) met need and 65 (65%) unmet need. Age group 35-49 AOR 2.277(1.452,3.612),Secondary educational status [AOR 3.638[1.216,10.886],No formal education AOR 4.903[1.104,10.777],un Employed participant AOR 3.355[2.151,5.126],Being student 4.885[2.385,6.024] , Number of give birth 3 and 4 [AOR 1.795[(0.056,3.73)],Gravida having more than four 0.221[0.061,0.804], LAFP Methods You heard? [AOR 2.498[1.178, 5.298] and Good attitude [AOR 2.327[1.114, 4.939] were found predictors of the demand for LAFPM in this study.

Table 9 Multivariable analysis for factors associated with LAFPM among women who attend family planning service at public health facilities in Debre birhane (n=390)

Variable	Options	Demand			AOR (95% CI)
		Good Demand%	Poor Demand %	P-value	
Age	15-24	119	26	0.01	1.00
	25-34	113	39	0.049	1.579(0.199,2.658)
	35-49	58	35	0.018 *	2.762(1.328,4.997)
Religion	catholic	10	6	0.020	1.00
	Muslim	23	10	0.666	0.725(0.259,2.299)
	Orthodox	194	54	0.929	0.464(0.196,0.934)
	Protestant	63	20	0.59	0.529(0.484,2.216)
Education	Elementary	114	14	0.001	1.00
	Secondary	50	19	0.003*	3.094(2.265,8.140)
	Diploma and above	110	58	0.004	4.294(1.706,12.295)
	No formal education	16	9	0.001**	4.58(1.438,6.658)
Occupation	Daily laborer	27	6	0.434	1.00
	Government Employee	43	10	0.003	1.046(0.486,5.371)
	Non-government Employee	36	8	0.647	1.000(1.753,3.265)
	House wife	61	13	0.047	0.959(0.222,1.729)
	Private business	75	34	0.747*	2.04(1.227,3.894)

	Student high school and above	34	16	0.002 *	2.117(1.015,6.870)	4.885(2.385,6.024)
	Unemployed	14	13	0.688*	4.178(2.129,5.868)	3.355(2.151,5.126)
Age at first marriage	15-24	52	15	0.942	1.00	1.00
	25-35	90	57		2.195(1.235,3.884)	2.606(1.221,4.659)
How many births have you given?	0-2	160	35	0.260	1.00	1.00
	3 and 4	111	52		2.142(1.309,3.503)	8.976(2.596,13.671)
	>4	19	13		3.128(1.413,6.924)	4.286(2.776,9.685)
How many of them are alive?	0-2	149	28		1.00	1.00
	3 and 4	118	57	0.050	2.571(1.539,4.293)	1.795(0.056,3.73)
	>4	23	15	0.260*	3.470(1.614,7.462)	0.221(0.061,0.804)
Have you ever had exposure to long-acting contraceptive message through mass media within the last 12 months?	Yes	128	18	0.001	1.00	1.00
	No	162	82		3.599(1.159,5.487)	3.244(1.294,4.23)
If yes, please mention LAFP Methods You heard?	Implanon	144	26		1.00	1.00
	IUCD	116	66		3.151(1.882,5.277)	2.498(1.178,5.298)
Attitude	Poor attitude	85	16		1.00	1.00
	Good attitude	205	84	0.010 *	2.177(1.254,4.830)	2.327(1.114,4.939)

6. Discussion

This study assessed the demand for long-acting family planning methods (LAFPMs) and associated factors among family planning service users in Debre Birhan. Most respondents were aged 25–34 (39%), married (44.1%), and had primary education (43.1%). About 74.1% of women had a positive attitude toward LAFPMs. The overall demand for LAFPMs was 25.6%, with only 9% of all respondents meeting their need, while 16.6% had an unmet need, often relying on short-acting methods despite preferring long-acting ones.

Awareness was generally high: 90.3% had heard of LAFPMs, mainly from health professionals (41.4%). Knowledge was also strong, with 80% scoring good knowledge. Most understood that IUCDs and implants prevent pregnancy, do not interfere with sexual activity, and in the case of implants, fertility returns quickly after removal.

Compared to other settings, demand in this study (25.6%) was lower than in Iran (71.3%) (26), Sidama (37.8%) (23), and Asosa (62.9%) (41), but higher than in Kenya (18%) (28), Nepal (11%) (32), and Northwest Ethiopia (17%) (10,33). It was similar to Oromia (28.4%) (34). Regional differences may reflect variations in population, study periods, autonomy in contraceptive choice, and access to services.

Predictors of demand identified in this study included age, marital status, gravidity, education, media exposure, and attitude. Women aged 35–49 were more than twice as likely to demand LAFPMs (AOR = 2.28). Secondary education (AOR = 3.64), no formal education (AOR = 4.90), being a student (AOR = 4.88), and unemployment (AOR = 3.36) were all significantly associated. Multigravida women (AOR = 2.22), those with three or more births, and women not planning further children (AOR = 2.17) were more likely to demand LAFPMs. Joint decision-making with husbands (AOR = 2.73), frequent spousal discussions, and prior information exposure (AOR = 2.50) also increased demand. Positive attitude doubled the likelihood of demand (AOR = 2.33).

These findings align with other Ethiopian studies showing that education, gravidity, spousal involvement, and knowledge strongly predict LAFPM uptake (14,33,36,42). Conversely, poor provider–client interaction and lack of counseling remain barriers (10,44).

Overall, while knowledge and awareness are high, demand and utilization of LAFPMs in Debre Birhan remain low, with a considerable unmet need. Strengthening counseling, improving provider–client communication, addressing misconceptions, and empowering women—particularly students and younger women—may help close this gap.

6 Strength and limitation of study

Strength of study

- The questioner was pretested on similar setting and possessed high response rate and employed a straightforward random sample technique, the sampling strategy and process reduced selection bias.

Limitation of the study

- The limitation of this study was cross-sectional nature of the data that temporal relationship between exposure and outcome variable could not be established

7 This study was conducted among only family planning service users in the government facilities; y not representative to general population.

CONCLUSION

Demand of LAFPM was found low 100 (25.6%) among women in Debre Birhane who attended family planning service in public health facilities. Factor which are associated with long-acting family planning method are Gravida status, Multigravida, Information from mass media, attitude on LAFPM, Age 35-49 education No formal education age at marriage 25-35 and being student. And No employment show association with demand for LACM by the bivariate analysis.

8 RECOMMENDATION

Recommendation to Debre Birhane Health Department

Having positive attitude for LAFPM show high demand for LAFPM compared to those who have negative attitude so it is better to address the attitude of community on birth control effect of LAFPM, as it has less side effect compared to others, and give information clearly to the community. by using Information from mass media,

Health centers

- Expected to do more to Arrange time and place where short and brief health education related to family planning especially LAFPM can be given for those client who come to the institution for family planning, ANC, safe abortion care service and postnatal mother come for vaccine.
- Assign and continuously follow those health care provider who were assigned to provide health education related to reproductive health mainly long acting family planning to those who have 3 and more birth, No formal education, and age at marriage 25-35.
- To do more by assigning health care provider to provide the outreach health education program related to the role of Long acting family planning and counselling's session to the community reproductive women's, husband and any concerned body who play role in the contraceptive utilization.

Community leaders

- Expected to do more to increase the involvement of husband or partners on shared decision making and give them education related to the role of family planning to maintain reproductive health at different setting like social meeting area in the community (Idir, conference and the

like).

Research Institutes and researchers

- A more intense qualitative and quantitative studies especially in the community settings are needed to gain further insight on acceptance of Long term family planning by reproductive women, their husband and community religious leaders.

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